

Deliverable D9.2: DMP and open data use plan -1

Deliverable information

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Project description

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Today 2.5 million tonnes of composite material are in use in the wind energy sector globally. Wind turbine blades are made up of composite materials that allow lighter and longer blades with optimised aerodynamic shape, which boost the performance of wind energy. However, current wind blade composites exhibit relatively short life spans, are problematic to repair and are notoriously difficult to recycle. As we continue to build more wind farms these issues pose a major problem to achieving a truly sustainable European wind energy sector.

EOLIAN project will develop an innovative new smart wind turbine blade, manufactured from a recyclable circular platform chemistry (vitrimers) and basal fibres, with sensors and heating actuators that detect damage early before it becomes a major issue. In the project, we will validate these performance claims through the manufacture, testing and benchmarking of a smart sensor-assisted vitrimer-based composite 14m prototyped wind blade. Additionally, we will prove circular recyclability through the manufacture of 2nd generation composites with recycled fibers and recycled vitrimer obtained after the chemical recycling by vacuum infusion and with composite parts produced by SMC following mechanical recycling.

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Abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation / Acronym	Description
WP	Work Package
EU	European Union
EC	European Commission
INEA	Innovation & Networks Executive Agency, an agency of the European Commission
HE	Horizon Europe - the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2021-2027)
CFS	Certificate of the Financial Statement
VAT	Value Added Tax (a sales tax)
TBC	To be confirmed
GA	Grant Agreement
DMP	Data Management Plan

Project coordinator		
1	PROP	Proplast - Consorzio per la promozione della cultura plastica
Project beneficiaries		
2	POLM	Politecnico di Milano
3	ZOREN	Zorlu Enerji Elektrik Üretim AS
4	IRES	Ires - innovation in research and engineering solutions
5	NORV	Norvento tecnologia, s.l.
5.1	NNF	Norvento ned factory, s.l.u. (<i>affiliate partner to Norv</i>)
6	TEK	Fundacion Tekniker
7	EuCIA	Association Europeenne de l'industrie des Composites
8	AEP	AEP polymers srl
Project associated partners		
9	BUL	Brunel University London
10	ENT	Entelea limited

1 Introduction

The Data Management Plan (DMP) summarizes the way that the data collected or generated within the project will be organized, stored, and shared.

The first audience to which this report is addressed is the internal partnership. EOLIAN partnership is made of 10 partners. The DMP, since the early phase of the project, will support partners in considering all the relevant aspects of data management, by establishing consistent practices among partners to increase the efficiency and robustness of data handling along the project. The second audience of the DMP is the community of researchers, policy makers, stakeholders, interested in re-using datasets produced by EOLIAN.

This document is the initial version of the DMP to be delivered at Month 6. The complex structure of the project, the heterogeneity of the experimentation sites, and the workplan will require updates of the DMP that will be consolidated in the deliverables D9.4 and D9.6, to be delivered at project's M24 and at the end of the project (M36), respectively. New versions of DMP should reflect changes, such as those due to modifications in consortium composition or implementation of new regulations, external factors, such as the emergence of new data standards, new releases of external datasets reused by EOLIAN, and, finally, the inclusion and the documentation of new datasets produced by the project according to the workplan.

This deliverable is structured according to the HE templates. Section 2 (Data Summary) provides general information about the data usage in the project, namely the purpose and sources of data collection/generation in relation to the achievement of projects goal. Technical information about data formatting and size will be provided. The Section 3 (FAIR data) will describe the general methodologies that the project will follow to ensure that data will be managed according to the FAIR principles and recommended FAIR practices, with subsections specifically targeting the basic elements of FAIR principles. Subsequent sections will deal with the Allocation of resources, Data security and Ethical aspects. Section 5 (Allocation of resources) details how project resources are allocated to the management of research data. Section 6 (Data security) explains what provisions are or will be in place for data security. Section 7 (Ethics) is about ethics and legal issues could have an impact on data sharing.

For each dataset that is released, relevant information will be provided highlighting specific methods adopted to be compliant with FAIR objectives. It is expected that this section will be enriched with the description of new datasets as the EOLIAN progresses in implementing its work plan.

It is expected that EOLIAN will generate a significant amount of research data including (but not limited to) vitrimer polymers and composite characteristics data, composite processing and product data. New datasets will be generated and new insights from existing data sources will be developed. A key challenge is to ensure the impartiality and accuracy of any data collected since data can become biased towards an individual or organisation's objectives and secondary data may be misinterpreted if they were collected for a different purpose. To mitigate these weaknesses, we will compare our results with those obtained from reliable data/information sources.

2 Data Summary

EOLIAN project will generate and collect data during the planned work to develop a bio-based, repairable and recyclable vitrimer composites and advanced sensors for highly reliable and sustainable wind blades. The data collected/gathered will allow enabling the achievement of the objectives of the project, namely to:

1. Development of a biobased vanillin-based polyimine vitrimer which is suitable to be used in composite production by vacuum infusion.
2. Development of a vitrimer-based composite by vacuum infusion (i) whose performance is at least equal to traditional thermoset composites (epoxy / unsaturated polyester / vinyl esters); (ii) which are easily repairable; (iii) bio- (the vitrimer) and natural- (the fibres) based; (iv) reusable and recyclable.
3. Enable seamless integration of recyclable sensors and heater actuators using in-mould electronics for composite materials, ensuring robust functionality and reliability through thorough characterization and formulate effective optimization and control methodologies for sensor-actuator systems on wind turbine blades.
4. Production of a smart, sensor-assisted vitrimer-based composite wind blade with a processing technology and time which are comparable to the traditional wind blades production and whose environmental impact is lower than the traditional counterpart.
5. Development of 2nd generation composites with (i) recycled fibres and recycled vitrimer obtained after the chemical recycling by vacuum infusion; (ii) with composite parts obtained through SMC (Sheet Mould Compound) following mechanical recycling.
6. Carry out detailed Life Cycle Analyses and Socio-economic Assessments – confirmation that EOLIAN delivers superior environmental, economic and social benefits when benchmarked against existing composite blade solutions.

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Data collected will primarily be for the purposes of:

- development of vanillin-based vitrimer chemistry;
- development of vitrimer-based composite reinforced with basalt fibres;
- development of sensors (corrosion and ice detectors) and actuators (heaters) to manufacture the composite;
- construction of 3D molecular epoxy-vitrimer models' representative of the actual material under study;
- assessment of the effect of dynamic covalent bonding epoxy-hardener on thermomechanical and physio-chemical properties;
- formulation of an accurate and comprehensive finite element (FE) material card with the molecular modelling output;
- designing of a wind blade prototype consisting of all the EOLIAN technical developments;
- evaluation of the sustainability (Life Cycle Analyses and Socio-economic Assessments) and risk assessment;
- general project dissemination and communication (images, graphics, reports)

New data will be originated by the all the project activities, for example:

- experimental data will come from the vitrimer synthesis (e.g. chemical analysis, thermal analysis, mechanical testing data), sensors and actuators validation, vitrimer composite computational models, scale-up of technical achievement to manufacture a wind blade prototype. Both raw and derived data will be recorded and filed;
- images, e.g. photo to document the project progress,

- videos, e.g. short movies, animations to document the activities, represent and communicate achievements etc.
- interviews will be conducted to people within and outside the project consortium;
- multimedia documents: published or confidential reports, spread sheets, presentations, website contents, social media posts.

EOLIAN project is expected to generate/gather:

- experimental data;
- models;
- wind blade design schemes;
- multimedia documents;
- photos.

Types and formats of data generated/collected:

- Microsoft Office file format will be the reference for documents, spreadsheets and presentations; Documentation draft and published manuscripts, project reports and deliverable documents will be stored also in a Portable Document Format (PDF) (.pdf);
- Data coming from measurements will be in original format - depending on the sensor/application used to get the measure - then exported to ASCII file using TXT and CSV format;
- Images will be stored in JPEG/TIFF compressed format;
- Audio files will be stored in MP3/MP4 format;
- Videos in AVI code.

Expected size of data is currently unknown, however wherever possible, the best compromise between storage efficiency and accessibility of information will be sought. For example:

- photos and pictures will be most likely stored in JPEG/TIFF compressed format, unless high resolution is required e.g. for publishing purposes;
- images will be included in documents (e.g. reports) in such a way not to increase significantly the dimension of the files;
- compressed folders (e.g. .zip or .rar) might be used, mainly for sharing purposes, but an uncompressed version of the data will be archived for backup.

The data generated within the project will be used mainly by the beneficiaries and associated partners for undertaking the activities required to reach the project objectives. The use of the results, to which data are likely to constitute a fundamental part, is regulated by the Consortium Agreement. If the data generated are not deemed confidential or instrumental for commercial exploitation, including means of protection of generated IPR, they will be disclosed by publication on the project website, public area (for reports, including deliverables classed as public within the project Grant Agreement); Zenodo Public Repository for raw/elaborated data (mainly numeric data). Amongst such data, we foresee as a minimum to publish data used to produce the projects scientific publications.

At this initial stage, mainly project reports and deliverables are planned to be shared in open access, because they include elaborate and interpreted results, obtained from specific and detailed lists of tests that ensure clarity and scientific value for external users. The partners consider interpretation and contextualization essential to avoid misinterpretation of raw or partially processed datasets, which may lack standalone meaning. During the project, partners will evaluate the possibility of making datasets available, provided this does not conflict with patents or scientific publications, and when they consider them truly useful to others. In fact, when the datasets are not openly accessible, the restrictions will fall under the following categories:

- **Legal reasons:** Compliance with GDPR and national regulations on personal data protection. Sensitive or personal data will be anonymized or pseudonymized where feasible; otherwise, access will be restricted.
- **Contractual reasons:** Data obtained from external providers or subject to third-party agreements will remain confidential.
- **Legitimate interests:** Results intended for commercial or industrial exploitation may be temporarily closed until intellectual property protection (e.g., patenting) is secured.

Table below summarizes the datasets of EOLIAN project.

Dataset Number	Data Description	WP	Partner resp.	Data Origin	Data Type(s)	Data Format	Approx. data size	Sharing method
1	Wind blade material requirements	1	Norvento	Back-ground of Norvento's workers, material datasheet, previous test of materials	Text documents, Excel files	*.docx, *.xlsx	Less than 10 GB	Data properties and process description: confidential - Industrial Property (IP)
2	Description of procedures and experimental results for vitrimer synthesis	2	Proplast	Laboratory experiments and testing (e.g. chemical syntheses and formulation, quality control, performance characterizations, etc.)	Text documents, Excel and Origin Lab files, PowerPoint presentations	*.docx, *.xlsx, *.pptx, *.opju, *.jpeg, *.tiff, *.png	Less than 10 GB	When licence allows, whenever it does not conflict with patenting / publications, to be shared on Zenodo. Scientific articles to be published open access.
3	Description of procedures and experimental results for vitrimer synthesis	2	Tekniker	Laboratory experiments and testing (e.g. chemical syntheses and formulation, quality control, performance characterizations, etc.)	Text documents, Excel files, images and PowerPoint presentations	*.docx, *.xlsx, *.pptx, *.jpeg, *.tiff	Less than 10 GB	When licence allows, whenever it does not conflict with patenting / publications, to be shared on Zenodo. Scientific articles to be published open access.
4	Description of procedures and experimental results for composite development	2	POLIMI	Laboratory experiments and testing (e.g. composite manufacturing procedures, mechanical testing, etc.)	Text documents, Excel files, images and video files, PowerPoint presentation, technical drawings and 3D models.	*.docx, *.xlsx, *.pptx, *.jpeg, *.tiff, *.mp4, *.dxf, *.stl	Between 10 and 50 GB	When licence allows, whenever it does not conflict with patenting / publications, to be shared on Zenodo. Scientific articles to be published open access.
5	Description of Molecular Modelling Workflow and Modelling Predictions	3	Entelea	Molecular Modelling predictions (material properties) and animations	Text documents, Excel files, images, video files	*.txt, *.xlsx, *.jpeg, *.png, *.mp4	Less than 10 GB	When licence allows, whenever it does not conflict with patenting / publications, to be shared on Zenodo. Scientific articles to be published open access.
6	Description of Mechanical Modelling Workflow and Modelling Predictions	3	Brunel	Mechanical modelling predictions (material properties)	Text documents, Excel files, images, video files	*.txt, *.xlsx, *.jpeg, *.png, *.mp4	Less than 10 GB	When licence allows, whenever it does not conflict with patenting / publications, to be shared on Zenodo. Scientific articles to be published open access.

7	State of the Art of blade manufacturing and In mould electronics for sensors and actuators.	4	Tekniker	SoA of blade manufacturing and In mould electronics focused on materials and methods.	Text documents and power point presentations	*.docx, *.pdf, *.pptx	Less than 10 GB	When licence allows, whenever it does not conflict with patenting / publications, to be shared on Zenodo.
8	Description of manufacturing procedures of sensors and actuators	4	Tekniker	Laboratory experiments and testing (e.g., material compatibility test results, demonstrator characterisation) and demonstrator design and manufacturing process.	Text documents, excel files, and power point presentations	*.docx, *.pdf, *.pptx, *.xlsx	Less than 10 GB	Eolian Website & Public deliverables shared on Zenodo
9	Prototype integrating sensors and actuators on EOLIAN composites	4	Tekniker	Successful manufactured prototype integrating sensing and heating system. Description and validation of the system	Text documents, excel files, images	*.docx, *.pdf, *.xlsx	Less than 10 GB	When licence allows, whenever it does not conflict with patenting / publications, to be shared on Zenodo.
10	Description of procedures and experimental results for vitrimer scale up	5	AEP	Laboratory experiments and testing (e.g. chemical syntheses and formulation, quality control, performance characterizations, etc.)	Text documents, excel files, images and video files, PowerPoint presentations	*.docx, *.xlsx, *.pptx, *.jpeg, *.tiff, *.mp4	Less than 10 GB	When licence allows, whenever it does not conflict with patenting / publications, to be shared on Zenodo.
11	Wind blade design	5	Norvento	Computer simulation, Excel files.	Text documents, excel files, images and PowerPoint presentations	*.docx, *.xlsx, *.jpeg, *.tiff, *.pptx	Less than 30 GB	Traditional blade: to be shared on Zenodo. Vitrimer blade: confidential - Industrial Property (IP)
12	Wind blade manufacture	5	Norvento	Manufacturing process and testing sections of blades (specimens smaller than blades)	Images and video files	*.jpeg, *.mp4	Less than 30 GB	Shared on Zenodo. Infusion setup and laminates stackup: confidential - Industrial Property (IP)
13	Design and manufacturing challenges	5	Norvento	Outcomes of the EOLIAN project	Text documents	*.docx/ *.pdf	Less than 10 GB	Shared on Zenodo.
14	Risk evaluation results	7	IRES	Estimated, observational, measured, analysed, literature	Text documents, excel files, images, PowerPoint presentations, instrument specific	*.docx, *.txt, *.pdf, *.xlsx, *.csv, *.pptx, *.jpeg, *.jpg,	Less than 10 GB	Shared on Zenodo.

					format used to interact with data processing software	*.png, *.tiff, instrument-specific format		
15	LCA / LCC / sLCA result	7	IRES	Estimated/Compiled (Data coming from analysis or compilation)	Text documents, Excel files, images and PowerPoint presentations	*.docx, *.xlsx, *.pptx, *.jpeg	Less than 10 GB	Public deliverables shared on Zenodo
16	Intellectual property strategy, patent searches, technology monitoring reports, and inter-partner property sharing matrices.	8	Zorlu	Analysis of international patent databases, legal assessments of technical outputs, and contractual negotiations between consortium members.	Text documents, Excel files, images and PowerPoint presentations	*.docx, *.xlsx, *.pptx, *.jpeg	Less than 1 GB	Secure Cloud Storage (SharePoint) with restricted access rights
17	Survey on gender equality perspectives	8	EuCIA	Findings of online survey of EOLIAN partners	PowerPoint/pdf files	*.pptx, *.pdf	Less than 10 GB	Shared on EOLIAN website
18	EOLIAN media library	8	EuCIA	Project images for media organisations for external communications	Image files, videos	*.jpg, *.png, *.mp4	Less than 10 GB	Shared on EOLIAN website
19	EOLIAN video library	8	EuCIA	Project videos for external communications	Video files	*.mp4	Less than 10 GB (individual files)	Shared on EOLIAN YouTube channel

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An updated list of datasets will be given in the next version of the DMP (planned to be submitted at M24, May 2026).

With respect to data of a personal nature, anonymization is proposed to be used as a main strategy to ensure protection of personal data, and any publication of such elaborated data will be regulated according to the regulations in force.

Once the data documents will be made public according to the GA and CA procedures, resin producers and other wind blade manufacturers would be potentially interested in use them to pave the way for a general exploitation of the technology developed in the project.

Re-use of existing data. Existing data might be used to provide, for instance, benchmarks for evaluations of benefits of chosen materials and manufacturing solutions. Such data will be gathered from sources such as learned papers, established industry publications, other studies of recognized value and/or clear reliability (e.g.: previous research undertaken by partners where methodology of data collection is known and approved, studies published by international organisations). Wherever pre-existing data will be used, their source will be logged by the user, and clear reference made to it, including either a link to it (if available online) and/or publishing information (if no online reference existed).

The Coordinator of EOLIAN Project encourages partners to make existing data available for research within the project Consortium. To support such data re-use, lists of datasets collected and generated during the course of the project will be made available on the EOLIAN website, and access procedures drafted for those data. If relevant in their research task, the consortium partners should be able to make use of these existing data.

3 FAIR data

3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

To make data FINDABLE, the EOLIAN project team will ensure each file of data is accompanied by a set of metadata to aid discoverability.

For the data stored internally and shared amongst partners, the consortium will strive to adopt the same standards for consistency, with the following list of fields mandatory:

- file size;
- file extension;
- info about when the file was created;
- info about who created the file (name and affiliation);
- a reference to the project (acronym and GA number).

Metadata in Microsoft Office files are stored in the “Properties” field accompanying each file, which can be completed/modified according to the above requirements; for other formats, guidelines from the software provider will be sought. For pictures, metadata can be added with photo editor software (proprietary or open source) or with other tools (like file management tools enabling metadata editing). For the data shared amongst the partners but unpublished, each version will be named with the extension “_v<version number>” with numbers starting from 1. Each new version will contain details of the versioning in the metadata, according to the standard provided, and/or details in the associate entry in the readme.txt.

Moreover, in order to guarantee the correct interpretation of the data structure and the reproducibility of the obtained results, testing information and procedures (followed standard, testing parameters, environmental condition during testing), along with the used equipment and its settings (acquisition rate, data resolution, ...), will be made available with the experimental data. This will be done either within the files that report the results, or in a separated text file that will be saved in the same folder of the experimental data files.

3.2 Making data accessible

3.2.1 Repository

A Zenodo community has been opened by Proplast and can be found at this link: <https://zenodo.org/communities/eolian-project/>. In this repository, all the open-access documents and the datasets which are declared to be shared open access, will be constantly uploaded. All the partners, under the supervision of the coordinator, will oversee this task. The use of Zenodo is

free of charge, while a small budget for scientific paper publications has been set aside for the participants. Preservation of data on Zenodo is expected to be free of charge for the foreseeable future.

As for the internal sharing of data, all documents produced in the project will be stored and archived on the extranet site (Microsoft Teams repository), with a folder for each work package including the WP9 Project Management and additional folders for General Documents, Meetings and Administrative documents. The Deliverables will be uploaded in a specific folder of the General section: working reports will be uploaded in the WP folders, and documents related to meetings will be uploaded in the Meeting folders.

The assignment and management of persistent identifiers to the data will be assessed in the course of the project and will be described in the project DMPs. It is recommended to use Uniform Resource Identifier (URI) to facilitate links between different data. Most repositories are providing automatically persistent identifiers such as DOI, e.g. the functionality provided by Zenodo platform.

3.2.2 Data

Data, including deliverables, produced in the course of the project should be made openly available as the default, while respecting compliance with European and national ethic-legal framework on personal data protection.

Depending on the deliverables, restrictions might apply for specific reasons that will be stated in the overarching DMP and in project DMPs for each research or integrative project. Similarly, restrictions can be foreseen for other scientific data used/generated during the projects and will be described in specific project DMPs. The rationale for keeping data closed might include:

1. Open access is incompatible with the obligation to protect results that can reasonably be expected to be commercially or industrially exploited: In general, open access does not affect the decision to exploit research results commercially, e.g. through patenting. The decision on whether to publish through open access must come after the more general decision on whether to publish directly or to first seek protection.
2. Open access is incompatible with rules on protecting personal data: protection of the personal right needs to be ascertained either by avoiding open access to sensitive and personal data, or by anonymizing the data if relevant and feasible.
3. Open access is incompatible with the need for confidentiality in connection with data from external owners/providers.

To help partners in their decision to use open access, restricted access or keeping data closed, the DMP team will provide a decision tree. Therefore, the access to publications or research data, will be data specific. The decision to select a specific type of access (open, restricted or close) will be under the responsibility of the individual project partners which collected/processed/generated the data, and the rationale to keep data closed will be described in the project DMPs.

Specify what methods, codes or software tools are needed to access the data for most data, only standard software, e.g. web browsers, pdf-file readers, and text readers, will be needed. Where non-standard tools are used, procedures to access the data will be documented in the project DMPs.

EOLIAN deliverables and data can either be public or sensitive. Some results might be restricted in their use. Sensitive and personal data can be made accessible only following the GDPR requirements. The aim is to reach the highest level of GDPR compliance, amongst others by:

- Relying on the EU authentication platform and security protocols for data sharing.
- Applying a strict policy in granting and revoking access to the data.
- Logging of user identity during data access, download, and upload, including version control. As several repositories will be used to store data, the policy on how to grant access to restricted results will be developed over the course of the project and described in project DMPs.

By default, data generated with EOLIAN funding and accompanying metadata are directly accessible for use within EOLIAN. For sensitive data, the data owner/data provider shall agree in the transfer of the data at high level of granularity to an EOLIAN defined repository, using appropriate measures to anonymise data. Prior to generation of the data, the data owner/data provider shall confirm ethico-legal compliance of the study in which new data are generated.

For existing data, not generated with EOLIAN funding, the data owner/data provider specifies the level of granularity that data will be stored and/or transferred: anonymised single measurement data; pseudonymised single measurement data; or aggregated data. The data owner/data provider indicates for each level of granularity whether the data are directly accessible for use within the EOLIAN. In case the data owner/data provider indicates that the data are not directly accessible for use within EOLIAN, the data owner/data provider will be asked approval when consortium members request access to the data to meet the goals of a particular objective.

3.2.3 Metadata

Metadata of publications will be deposited in Zenodo and open under a Creative Common Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or equivalent for 10 years at least, providing information about author(s), title, date of publication, publication venue; Horizon Europe funding; grant project name, acronym and number; licensing terms; persistent identifiers for the publication, the authors involved in the action and, if possible, for their organisations and the grant. Where applicable, the metadata must include persistent identifiers for any research output or any other tools and instruments needed to validate the conclusions of the publication.

Publication on Zenodo entails the generation of a Zenodo Digital Object Identifiers. Every effort will be made to ensure that the data/publications are made available on the repositories in their definitive version.

Zenodo uses Digital Object Identifiers (DOI) making data and metadata citable and easily discoverable. DOI is resolvable, persistent and globally unique. Data files are versioned; each version has its own unique DOI. Data is also linked to EC project topic identifier. On creation of record, metadata is indexed and searchable on Zenodo's engine and is sent to and indexed on DataCite servers

As an aid to identify and making searchable the data files, the naming will be developed to include most of the following information, as applicable:

- Project or experiment name or acronym
- Date or date range of experiment

- Type of data
- WP identification
- Version number of file

Naming convention: EO_Data_WP#_v1

Wherever possible, tags or keyword will be associated with the files to make them searchable according to themes. For files in Microsoft Office format, this can be done either upon saving a new file or working on the properties of the files; for other file formats, this will be explored by the beneficiary generating the file.

Because of the potential confidentiality, however, some of the data generated within the project might not be publishable because of IPR issues. Such data are likely to be still exchanged internally e.g. as results required to progress towards the objectives of the project, and their internal use is regulated by the Consortium Agreement. The consortium will decide whether data not published because of IPR issues might be publishable once IPR protected. Restricted access might be considered e.g. for some categories of data – e.g. those for which the consortium is interested or required to collect information about the potential external usage, for example the mobility application.

3.3 Making data interoperable

The degree of interoperability of data generated is expected to be high, common formats of files and metadata recognized standards will be used. Metadata specialist will be used, a definition will be provided into a “Notes” or “Comments” field or within the readme.txt file within the folder where the files are stored.

If there is a lack of metadata standards, the consortium will reuse existing controlled vocabularies for providing metadata to resources as far as possible. A controlled vocabulary is a predefined list of values to be used as values for a specific property in your metadata schema. In addition to careful design of schemas, the value spaces of metadata properties are important for the exchange of information, and thus interoperability.

Controlled vocabularies for reused can be found on Interoperable Europe (<https://interoperable-europe.ec.europa.eu/>) and Linked Open Vocabularies (<https://lov.linkeddata.es/dataset/lov/>) platforms. If there is no suitable authoritative reusable vocabulary for describing data, conventions will be used for describing the vocabulary: RDF Schema (RDFS) and/or Web Ontology Language (OWL). The best practice when new terms are required, is to define their range and domain. A range states that the values of a property are instances of one or more classes. A domain states on which classes a given property can be used. The new vocabulary should be published within a stable environment designed to be persistent. Existing resources from previous EU projects will serve as the basis for this work. In case the partners consider it necessary, EOLIAN project will create a data and metadata knowledge model for surveillance data.

English language will be used for all published and internally shared data, considering the international make-up of the consortium. If languages other than English are used, e.g. for interviews of local stakeholders, English transcripts/translations will be made available.

Any software product will be used and published as open data; a clear identification of the required operative system will be provided. The choice between the most common OSs might depend upon the specific software architecture and the in-built flexibility of the OS itself.

In case an uncommon or generate project, specific ontologies or vocabularies will be not available to be used, the project partners will provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies. The generated ontologies or vocabularies will be published.

The data will include qualified references to other data and the assignment and management of persistent identifiers to the data will be assessed in the course of the project and will be described in the project DMPs.

3.4 Increase data re-use

Both for internally shared data and for published data, every partner generating data will be responsible for the quality of their data in terms of content (e.g. only data from test run in valid conditions, advanced draft versions of documents, etc) and formalities for example elimination of outliers from numerical data; formatting, internal referencing, correct use of pictures, etc in project reports.

Data for publication will need to meet the requirements set in this document (e.g. metadata, format as identified etc.). The Project Coordinator will check the overall quality of the data and their coherence with the requirements of the latest DMP and will work with the data owner for addressing any shortcomings.

Published datasets are primarily intended for downstream reuse by third parties and will be retained in Zenodo's repository for a minimum period of three years unless otherwise specified. Nevertheless, certain datasets may become obsolete within a shorter timeframe due to their intrinsic properties, such as format dependencies, temporal relevance, or domain-specific update cycles.

The provenance of the data will be thoroughly documented and verified using the appropriate standards.

DMPs will address research outputs other than data and will consider aspects related to the allocation of resources and ethical aspects (see Point 4 and 5).

4 Other research outputs

The management of other research outputs that could be generated/re-used in the project (e.g., software, models, new materials) will be discussed and, when relevant, their compliance to the FAIR principles will be detailed.

5 Allocation of resources

The policy of the Consortium is to apply the DMP starting from the data gathering phase, as retrofitting the specifications hereby included might be time consuming. As the data gathering/generating is responsibility of each partner as applicable, so it is the inclusion of the DMP requirements. Use of Zenodo is free of charge, while a small budget for scientific paper publications has been set aside for the participants. The partner EuCIA, who is in charge of the Dissemination and Exploitation workpackage, with the help of the Coordinator will be actively supporting all the other partners in identifying candidate data for publication. The Project Coordinator and the IP manager (EuCIA) will oversee ensuring data identified for publication are not jeopardizing and IPR protection through consultation with the workpackage leaders and

partners involved, also focusing on aspects related to preserve novelty of any publication under preparation.

6 Data security

For all data, every partner will be responsible for ensuring the data generated (raw or elaborated from other partner's data) are regularly backed up and stored safely according to internal safe keeping procedures. If such data is also shared internally at the Consortium, the data owner will be responsible also for the methods used to share information.

In addition, as some data might be shared with all members of the Consortium through proprietary cloud facilities.

As already reported in paragraph 2.2, the main documents produced in the project will be stored and archived on the extranet site (Microsoft Teams repository), with a folder for each work package including the WP9 Project Management and additional folders for General Documents, Meetings and Administrative documents. Working reports will be uploaded in the WP folders, and documents related to meetings will be uploaded in the Meeting folders. This system provides a continuous backup which allow one to recover any documents accidentally deleted. Finally, the Coordinator will be in charge of making a backup (at least once a month) on a local server.

7 Ethics

According to the definitions of the GDPR, the partners collecting personal data are the processors, while the controller, who is ultimately responsible for the data treatment, remains the Coordinator of the project. Every processor is given by the controller the responsibility for implementing every measure for ensuring the protection of the personal data.

Consent to collect and treat the data

The consent to film and audio-record the interviews will be asked and obtained before/at the beginning of each interview; similarly, for the questionnaires, the respondents will give their written consent to the treatment of the data.

To abide in full to the GDPR, Proplast and EuCIA will produce an informative to explain clearly how the data will be treated. This informative will be provided for gathering the consent of the people to be interviewed from such date.

Protection

The personal data are to be collected as much as possible in an anonymous form, and where that is not possible, they will be anonymized before any sharing. The processor undertaking such anonymization is required to keep separated any files containing trace of the personal details (name, contacts etc) from the anonymized data.

This is to avoid that image, opinions, statements etc. are reconducted to a specific person. Such files should be kept in a safe location to minimize data breach and destroyed after the time that will be stipulated within the informative. Password protection and encrypting might be used to enhance security of data. No personal details shall be shared with other partners of the project.

8 Other issues

No other procedures for data management are currently in use.

9 Conclusions

This deliverable has presented the initial structure of the EOLIAN project data management. The different sections can be modified and updated according to the needs that may arise during project implementation. The EOLIAN DMP is intended to be a “living document,” meaning that it will be revisited and revised as necessary throughout the project lifespan to reflect changes in project progression.

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